

Revisional Bariatric Surgery: Techniques for Managing Weight Recidivism and Surgical Complications

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Introduction

Bariatric surgery remains the most effective treatment for severe obesity and its related comorbidities. However, a considerable proportion of patients experience inadequate weight loss, weight recurrence, poor control of comorbidities, or procedure-related complications after primary surgery. As obesity is now recognized as a chronic and relapsing disease, revisional bariatric surgery has become an increasingly important part of long-term management. This review aimed to summarize the current evidence on revisional bariatric surgery, with focus on indications, preoperative evaluation, revisional options, and clinical outcomes.

Materials and methods

A structured literature search was performed following a narrative review approach. PubMed, Scopus, and Google Scholar were searched for relevant studies using terms related to revisional bariatric surgery, weight regain, bariatric surgery failure, conversion procedures, postoperative complications, and revision outcomes. Priority was given to peer-reviewed original studies, systematic reviews, and meta-analyses, particularly those published between 2020 and 2025, while older landmark studies were also included when relevant. Only English-language publications were considered.

Results

Revisional bariatric surgery is mainly performed for weight-related failure, including inadequate weight loss and weight recurrence, or for non-weight-related problems such as gastroesophageal reflux, dysphagia, anatomical complications, and nutritional or metabolic issues. Available revisional strategies include conversion to another bariatric procedure, augmentation of the primary operation, complication-directed revision, or restoration to normal anatomy. Procedure selection depends on the primary operation, the mechanism of failure, and patient-specific factors. The review also showed that endoscopic therapies, pharmacologic treatment, and robotic-assisted surgery are becoming more relevant in selected patients and may improve individualized management.

Conclusion

Revisional bariatric surgery plays a central role in the long-term treatment of obesity after suboptimal response to primary surgery. A structured, multidisciplinary, and individualized approach is essential to optimize outcomes and manage this complex group of patients.

Keywords

Revisional bariatric procedures; Weight recidivism; Sleeve gastrectomy; Roux-en-Y gastric bypass; Revisional surgery outcomes